

Hong-Ou-Mandel Effect and One Dimensional Reflection-Refraction

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We have suggested in previous notes that $\exp(ip_y)$, the free particle wavefunction, is really a complex probability (same modulus for any free particle p momentum) which allows for equal weights for any two AND (product) momenta in a 2-body scattering scenario if momentum is conserved, i.e. $\exp(ip_1y)\exp(ip_2y) = \exp(ip_3y)\exp(ip_4y)$ if $p_1+p_2 = p_3+p_4$ (momentum only in the y direction). This product AND scenario applies to two particles, but a single particle may be linked with an OR scenario which adds $\exp(ip_y)$ s for the same particle as in a 2-slit interference calculation if the slits are about \hbar/p apart.

These ideas may be applied to one dimensional reflection-refraction (which is discussed in (2)). If one thinks of $\exp(ip_y)$ as representing a probability, then an incident and reflected photon (same photon) interferes with itself as interference is simply OR probability (add) with time removed. The reason time may be removed is that this calculation may occur at the interaction point in which case the incident, reflected and refracted photon all exist at roughly the same time and Heisenberg uncertainty ensures that one cannot pinpoint an incident or reflected photon at an exact x and t . One then uses continuity of probability $\exp(ip_y)$ and the derivative $d/dy \exp(ip_y)$ to obtain the results of (1). We note that if one considers the case of a very tiny transmission, then the photon is essentially reflected, but there are still two cases $n_1 < n_2$ in which the reflected photon receives a phase of -1 and $n_1 > n_2$, in which case it does not. We suggest that these ideas may be applied to the Hong-Ou-Mandel effect.

We first remove $\exp(ip_x)$ s as they involve no interaction and only consider $\exp(ip_y)$ effects. We then note that if a photon reflects, it interferes with itself and one must consider a possible phase. Based on (2), one has one photon moving in the negative y direction and hitting a 50-50 reflection-transmission object with no phase change for reflection, and a photon moving in the y direction with a phase change of -1 on reflection. Thus, in the case of reflection-reflection, the self-interference leads to a -1 from the photon travelling in the positive y and a $+1$ from the photon travelling in the minus y direction when one multiplies OR terms for each photon (i.e. an AND situation of two self-interfering photons). In the case of both transmitting, one has $\exp(ip_y)\exp(-ip_y)$ (AND from each photon -no self-interference), but the sign is plus, so these two terms cancel and one only retains outcome terms with the two photons moving in the same direction with the same momentum, i.e. the bunching of the HOM effect.

We compare this approach of describing the HOM effect using the calculation of the 1-D reflection-refraction problem with a creation operator approach given in (1).

Mathematics of the Hong-Ou-Mandel Effect Using Creation Operators

The Hong-Ou-Mandel (HOM) effect involves two identical photons impinging on a device which allows for equal quantum amplitude (wavefunction) weights for reflection and transmission. The catch is that for the first photon moving down, a phase of $+1$ arises on reflection, while a phase of -1 for reflection for the second photon moving up occurs (as stated in (1)). Thus, one may consider four cases, 1-reflect 2-transmit, both reflect, both transmit,

1-transmit 2-reflect. Due to the -1 phase for the second reflection the middle two cases cancel and one has bunching, i.e. both photons move together.

The math developed in (1) to describe this is based on creation and annihilation operators i.e.

$$[ab] = (a^+)(b^+) |00\rangle \text{ transforms to } \{ (c^+) + (d^+) \} \cdot \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} \{ (c^+) - (d^+) \} |00\rangle \quad ((0))$$

Only the $(c^+)(c^+)$ and $(d^+)(d^+)$ terms survive which means that one has bunching of the photons. One may note that the -1 in $\{ (c^+) - (d^+) \}$ arises due to the reflection phase for the second photon reflection. Here (c^+) means transmission and (d^+) reflection. One may note that the math of $((0))$ is created to describe the amplitude diagrams (see (1)). We wish, however, to examine the problem in more detail in terms of the calculation of 1-dimensional reflection-refraction.

One Dimensional Reflection-Refraction and Phase Changes

In (1), it is argued that in the HOM effect, a photon which reflects from a beam splitter does not gain a phase if it is traveling in the minus y direction, but receives a phase of -1 if it is moving in the positive y direction. We suggest that this phase of -1 or +1 is akin to reflection from $n_1 < n_2$ (where n_2 is the index of refraction of the material) which produces -1 and reflection from $n_1 > n_2$ which produces +1. If one considers one dimensional reflection-refraction, then an incident photon must both reflect and refract. (We show that for $n_2=3$, $n_1=1$, one has equal amplitudes for reflection and refraction.) Furthermore, one may see that an incident photon interferes with its reflected self in a continuity equation. We argue that this idea is important for the analysis of the HOM factor because even though two photons are present, each photon interferes with itself. In the one dimensional reflection-refraction case one has OR situations because there is a single photon. With two photons, one has possible OR situations for each photon and then multiplies these together as an AND situation because there are two photons (one photon AND the other photon). We argue that one must understand the OR case first, because then one may simply multiply OR results together for each photon.

One dimensional reflection-refraction is based on single photon OR (probability addition) which may also be called self-interference. Two slit interference of a single photon is also an OR or self-interference scenario, but there are no continuity issues. In the 1D reflection-refraction case there are, because one has an index of refraction of n_1 on the LHS and n_2 , on the right. One may write a continuity equation of $\exp(ipx)$ probabilities as well one for the first derivative. {To recap how a complex probability with unit modulus arises, we note that free particles have the real probability for any p value. One may, however, wish to find a probability which ensures that given an elastic collision of two particles with total momentum P, (everything one dimensional), that any outcome pair p_i, p_j (momentum vectors in 1D) that add to P have the same probability (and the same condition for energy). This leads to $\exp(i C_1 E)$ and $\exp(i C_2 p)$, but due to Lorentz invariance conditions, one has $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$. In 1-D reflection refraction, energy remains the same for an incident, reflected or refracted photon) and so one only deals with $\exp(ipx)$.} The continuity equations are:

$$A \exp(ipx) + B \exp(-ipx) = C \exp(ip2x) \text{ at } x=0 \text{ where } n_1=1 \text{ and } p_2= p \cdot n_2 \text{ and } c_2=c/n. \quad ((1a))$$

$$A_p \exp(ipx) - B_p \exp(-ipx) = C_{p2} \exp(ip2x) \text{ at } x=0 \quad ((1b))$$

One may notice the self-interference or OR situation on the LHS of ((1a)). We also note that these probabilities do not represent the photon at the same time and so time effects have been removed. It is as if the probability (with $\exp(ipx)$ s) is done for steady streams of the incident, reflected and refracted photons.

In (2), it is shown that the results are:

$$B/A = (c_2 - c_1) / (c_2 + c_1) \quad \text{and} \quad C/A = 2c_2 / (c_1 + c_2) \quad ((2))$$

Then, for $c_2 > c_1$, $B > 0$ while for $c_2 < c_1$, $B < 0$. ((3))

Here AA, BB and CC are the fluxes of the incident, reflected and refracted photon. The actual probability balance equation is:

$$AA/c = BB/c + CC/c_2 \quad ((4))$$

In the Hong-Ou-Mandel effect case, one wishes to have $B=C$, i.e the same amplitude weight to reflect or transmit. This leads to:

$$n_2=3, \quad n_1=1 \quad ((5))$$

Hong-Ou-Mandel Effect Using the 1D Reflection-Refraction Approach

The approach of the HOM effect is to have two photons interact with a device with equal reflection-refraction (transmission) amplitudes. One photon reflects from $n_1 > n_2$ and the other from $n_1 < n_2$ and so the first photon will have a 1 phase reflection and the other. a -1 phase, but transmission and reflection have the same probability amplitude. Let us assume that the first photon moves down the y axis, and the second up. Then, for the first photon:

$(A \exp(-ipy) + [B] \exp(ipy))$ (reflection self-interference) Here [B] is a positive number always.

$[B] \exp(-ipy)$ (transmission)

Here we ignore $\exp(ipx)$ components because there is no interaction in the x-direction.

For the second photon, one has:

$(A \exp(ipy) - [B] \exp(-ipy))$ for reflection and $[B] \exp(ipy)$ for transmission ((6))

One may note that the same p is used in ((6)) because the refracted photon moves back out into an n_1 medium. We ignore any secondary reflections as in (1).

((6)) applies for each photon by itself. If one has two photons, this should be an AND probability scenario and so one must multiply outcome probabilities for each photon. One has:

$$1\text{-reflect } 2\text{-transmit} \quad \exp(ip_y) \exp(ip_y)$$

$$1\text{-transmit } 2\text{-transmit} \quad \exp(-ip_y)\exp(ip_y)$$

$$1\text{-reflect } 2\text{-reflect} \quad \exp(ip_y) (-1) \exp(-ip_y)$$

$$1\text{-transmit } 2\text{-reflect} \quad \exp(-ip_y)\exp(-ip_y) \quad ((7))$$

The transmit-transmit and reflect-reflect probability amplitudes cancel. This means that one does not see either or these and that only probabilities for 1-reflect 2-transmit or 1-transmit 2-reflect survive and so there is photon bunching. Basically, with probabilities one considers all possible results in the interaction region to see what outcomes are allowed. This is the same approach used for 2-slit interference except that one now has two photons which are identical. In other words, two photon interference occurs for the transmit-transmit and reflect-reflect processes which have the same appearance in a diagram (1). One may note that OR means add and one may add each AND term in ((7)) to create an overall OR (of internal ANDs). Thus, there can be interference among these OR terms as is the case for transmit-transmit and reflect-reflect. One may also note that transmit-transmit and reflect-reflect do not yield an $\exp(ip_y)$ type form, but rather a number 1.

We note that this analysis, based on 1D reflection-refraction differs in form from that of the first section (i.e. from (1)), i.e. the one which uses creation operators. It is based on the $\exp(ip_y)$ probabilities which are linked with equal probability for the same momentum.

Physical Meaning of the -1 Reflection Phase for $n_1 < n_2$

We argue that the -1 phase for reflection from $n_1 < n_2$ has meaning. In such a case, one has:

$A+B = C$ at $x=0$, but $A=1$ and C is positive and less than A . Here A and C are square root fluxes. This means that B must be a negative number. To see that C is less than A and still positive, one may consider the result from (2)

$$C/A = 2c_2 / (c_2 + c_1) \quad \text{where } c_1 = c \text{ and } c_2 = c/n_2 \text{ where } n_1 = 1 \text{ and } n_2 > 1. \text{ Then } c_2 < c_1 \text{ so } C/A < 1.$$

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that the results of the HOM effect follow from the analysis of 1-dimensional reflection refraction. If one has a single photon, one may use $\exp(ip_x)$ probabilities in OR situations. These still hold for each photon, but then one must multiply

outcome probabilities together because one has two photons, i.e. an AND situation. Finally, one adds the various scenario product probabilities as OR result which shows that the probabilities for both photons reflecting or both transmitting cancel. This then leaves 1-reflect 2-transmit or 1-transmit 2 reflect, which means that one has bunching of the photons, i.e. they move together. Even though a creation operator approach is introduced in (1) to describe this effect, we argue that one may resort to the calculation of the 1-D reflection-refraction problem to solve the problem.

References

1. https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Hong%E2%80%93Ou%E2%80%93Mandel_effect
2. https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Reflection_phase_change